

1 Prevalence of rotavirus among older children and adults with diarrhea: A systematic review and meta-analysis**2 Abstract**

3 *Background:* Older children and adults are susceptible to rotavirus, but the extent to which rotavirus affects this
4 population is not fully understood, hindering accuracy of global rotavirus estimations.

5 *Objective:* To determine what proportion of diarrhea cases are due to rotavirus among persons ≥ 5 years old and
6 to estimate this proportion by age strata.

7 *Methods:* We conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis using the PRISMA guidelines. We included
8 studies that reported on conditional rotavirus prevalence (i.e., percent of diarrhea due to rotavirus) in persons
9 ≥ 5 years old who were symptomatic with diarrhea/gastroenteritis and had laboratory confirmation for rotavirus
10 infection. Studies on nosocomial infections and outbreak investigations were excluded. We collected age group-
11 specific conditional rotavirus prevalence and other variables, such as study geography, study setting, and study
12 type. We calculated pooled conditional rotavirus prevalence, corresponding 95% confidence intervals (95% CI),
13 heterogeneity (I^2) estimates, and prediction intervals (PI).

14 *Results:* Sixty-six studies from 32 countries met the inclusion criteria. Conditional rotavirus prevalence ranged
15 from 0% to 30% across the studies. The total pooled prevalence of rotavirus among persons ≥ 5 years old with
16 diarrhea was 7.6% (95% CI: 6.2-9.2%, $I^2=99.6\%$, PI: 0–24%). The pooled prevalence of rotavirus among older
17 children and adolescents was 8.7% (95% CI: 6.2-11.7%, $I^2=96\%$, PI:0–27%), among younger adults was 5.4% (95%
18 CI: 1.4–11.8%, $I^2=96\%$, PI:0–31%), and among older adults was 4.7% (95% CI: 2.8–7.0%, $I^2=96\%$, PI:0–16%).
19 Pooled conditional rotavirus prevalences did not differ by other variables.

20 *Conclusion:* In this systematic review and meta-analysis of rotavirus among persons ≥ 5 years old with diarrhea,
21 we found relatively low pooled conditional rotavirus prevalence compared to what is typically reported for
22 children < 5 years; however, results should be interpreted with caution as the wide prediction intervals suggests
23 large heterogeneity.

24 **Prevalence of rotavirus among older children and adults with diarrhea: A systematic review and meta-analysis**

25 **Introduction**

26 Rotavirus is a leading cause of death due to diarrhea in children under 5 years of age, but it also affects older
27 children and adults [1]. Approximately 228,000 diarrhea deaths due to rotavirus occurred in 2016 among people
28 of all ages, with an estimated 45% of those occurring in people 5 years or older [1]. In 2013, the World Health
29 Organization (WHO) recommended the prioritization of rotavirus vaccination in national childhood
30 immunization programs [2]. While the introduction of the rotavirus vaccine has led to decreases in mortality in
31 young children [3], it is estimated that rotavirus continues to cause more than 200,000 deaths annually among
32 people of all ages [1]. Older children and adults are known to be susceptible to rotavirus infection, especially
33 those who are immunocompromised, elderly, or care for young children [4], but the extent to which rotavirus
34 affects people 5 years of age or older is not fully understood. Recent estimates of the diarrheal burden
35 attributed to different pathogens, including rotavirus, have been critiqued due to the limited data on disease
36 among older children and adults included in models [5]. To address this gap in knowledge, we conducted a
37 systematic review and meta-analysis to estimate the proportion of diarrhea cases due to rotavirus among older
38 children and adults globally.

39

40 **Methods**

41 We conducted a systematic review of the published literature and meta-analysis following PRISMA guidelines
42 [6]. The objective was to quantify the proportion of diarrhea cases due to rotavirus among persons ≥ 5 years old
43 and to estimate this proportion by age strata.

44

45 ***Literature search***

46 We searched the published literature cataloged in PubMed and EMBASE on April 5, 2019. To ensure a broad and
47 comprehensive search of the published literature, we modeled our search string after the terms the Institute of

48 Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME) uses to research diarrheal prevalence for the annual Global Burden of
49 Disease report. The full search strings used in our study can be found in Appendix 1.

50

51 ***Eligibility criteria***

52 Articles published in English from January 1, 1990 to April 5, 2019 were included in this systematic review if they
53 reported on rotavirus prevalence (i.e., percent of diarrhea due to rotavirus) in persons ≥ 5 years old who were
54 symptomatic with diarrhea/gastroenteritis and had laboratory confirmation for rotavirus infection. To be
55 included in this systematic review and meta-analysis, studies had to report on data for at least one year to
56 prevent bias due to the known seasonality of rotavirus infections. Studies were excluded if there was no
57 description of laboratory confirmation of rotavirus, e.g., diagnosis with ELISA, PCR, or PAGE, or if rotavirus was
58 due to a hospital-acquired infection. We excluded case studies, outbreak investigations, conference abstracts,
59 and systematic reviews. We included studies conducted in nursing homes or other institutions for the elderly,
60 but excluded studies conducted in special populations at high risk of outbreaks, namely among the military and
61 schools, which may artificially raise population estimates of rotavirus prevalence among diarrhea cases.

62

63 ***Study selection***

64 Each abstract was independently screened by two of three reviewers. In the event of a disagreement between
65 the two reviewers, all three reviewers would review the abstract and reach a consensus on whether to move the
66 abstract to full-text screening. Similarly, two reviewers independently assessed each full-text article to
67 determine eligibility for inclusion, and, in the event of a disagreement, all three reviewers reached consensus on
68 the article inclusion or exclusion. If it was unclear whether data on rotavirus prevalence may be available based
69 on the abstract, we moved the article to full-text review to ensure a more comprehensive review.

70

71 ***Data abstraction***

72 Two reviewers manually abstracted data from the studies included in this meta-analysis into a Microsoft Excel
73 workbook. Both the numerator (number of rotavirus cases) and denominator (total number of symptomatic
74 people tested for rotavirus) used to calculate the proportion of rotavirus-positive cases among individuals with
75 diarrhea, which we refer to in this paper as conditional rotavirus prevalence, were abstracted, along with the
76 corresponding ages for these datapoints. In some instances, relevant data on conditional rotavirus prevalence
77 were available in figures that did not provide exact numbers for the numerator and/or denominator. In such
78 instances, we used WebPlot Digitizer v4.2 to estimate count data [7]. Datapoints calculated using this program
79 were denotated in the dataset. Another reviewer assessed all data entries against the full-text articles to ensure
80 accuracy of data abstraction. Country-level data for each study were retrieved from outside sources and
81 incorporated into the dataset. Specifically, rotavirus vaccination status was retrieved from Johns Hopkins VIEW-
82 hub [8].

83

84 ***Data items***

85 The outcome of interest in this study was rotavirus positivity. We measured rotavirus positivity by conditional
86 rotavirus prevalence (i.e., the percentage of diarrhea cases testing positive for rotavirus) for people of eligible
87 ages (i.e., people ≥ 5 years old). We defined conditional rotavirus as the number of people with laboratory
88 confirmed rotavirus amongst the number of symptomatic people tested for rotavirus. The primary variable of
89 interest was the age range that corresponded to the conditional rotavirus prevalence. We obtained study-level
90 variables, namely: study geography (e.g., country, urban or rural), study setting (hospital inpatient, hospital
91 outpatient, hospital unspecified/both inpatient and outpatient, or community), date of data collection, study
92 type, sampling method, laboratory diagnostic method, and definition of symptoms that qualified patients to be
93 tested for rotavirus (i.e., WHO definition of diarrhea or other criteria). The WHO definition of diarrhea we used
94 in this study was 3 or more loose stools within 24 hours. We abstracted data for where the study was
95 conducted, namely region and rotavirus vaccination status. We defined region using the 2019 WHO world

96 regions and development level using the 2019 World Bank income regions. We defined rotavirus vaccination
97 status in country as whether national guidelines at/before the start of the study recommended rotavirus vaccine
98 as part of routine childhood vaccination.

99

100 **Age categorization**

101 We collected age data to account for potential differences in conditional rotavirus prevalence by age. Since
102 studies did not report cases by single year of age or standard age groups across all studies, we abstracted case
103 data needed to calculate conditional rotavirus prevalence (i.e., number of diarrhea cases tested for rotavirus and
104 number of rotavirus-positive cases) by the most granular age groups possible from each study. Based on these
105 age groups reported from each study and the hypothesized differences in conditional rotavirus prevalence by
106 age, we organized data into the following three age categories: “older children and adolescents” including ages
107 5–20 years, “younger adults” including ages 15–50 years, “older adults” including ages 50 years and older. Study
108 data reporting ages that span within any of the three age categories would be categorized as such (e.g., study
109 data reported for populations 5–9 years old would be categorized into the “older children and adolescents” age
110 category). Each study may contribute data to more than one age category. Note, while the “older children and
111 adolescents” and “younger adults” age categories have overlapping ages, no single study reported an age group
112 that would be place the same data in both categories (i.e., no double counting of cases across these three age
113 categories).

114

115 For some studies, the most granular age groups reported spanned multiple age categories. Data from these
116 studies were organized into two additional age categories: “broad adult ages” including age groups that spanned
117 across “younger adults” and “older adults” age categories and “broad all ages” including age groups that
118 spanned across child and adults ages.

119

120 Analysis

121 We conducted a meta-analysis of all data in our systematic review to calculate pooled conditional rotavirus
122 prevalence, and corresponding 95% confidence intervals (95% CI), heterogeneity (I^2) estimates, and prediction
123 intervals (PI) [9–11]. Statistics were conducted in R 3.6.1 (R Core Team, 2019) using the metaprop function in the
124 ‘meta’ package (v4.9-6) [12]. We used inverse variance weighting and arc sin transformation (i.e., final estimates
125 were back transformed) to stabilize the variance [10,13]. We used random effects in our model to allow the true
126 effect to vary from study to study [10].

127

128 We conducted sub-analyses to calculate the outcomes specified above (pooled prevalence, 95% confidence
129 intervals, heterogeneity, and prediction intervals) for conditional rotavirus prevalence by our primary variable of
130 interest (age strata) and our secondary variables of interest (WHO regions, income regions, study settings,
131 symptom definitions, data collection time period, and laboratory diagnostic method). We also assessed these
132 outcomes for each of the secondary variables of interest disaggregated by age strata. We generated forest plots
133 for all analyses, which are available in the Appendices.

134

135 Results**136 Study Selection**

137 We identified 3,815 unique abstracts between PubMed and Embase, of which we reviewed 690 in full text
138 (Figure 1). Fifty percent of studies reviewed in full text were excluded because they did not report conditional
139 rotavirus prevalence for persons aged 5 years or older (n=343). Ultimately, 66 studies were eligible to be
140 included in this review (Table 1).

141

142 Included Studies

143 The 66 studies included in this review represented 32 countries (Appendix 2). Most of these countries were
144 represented once in this review (n=18), but 11 of the studies included in this review were conducted in China
145 [14,15,24,16–23] and 7 were conducted in India [25–31]. The majority of studies were conducted in countries in
146 the European and the Western Pacific regions (n=39); only two eligible studies were found from the Africa
147 region [32,33] and no eligible studies were found from the Eastern Mediterranean region.

148

149 Approximately three-quarters of the included studies were conducted in upper-middle income or high-income
150 countries (n=51) (Table 2). Included studies were predominantly hospital-based. Two-thirds of the studies
151 included in this review were conducted in the last ten years, yet only three studies were conducted when there
152 were national guidelines in place that recommended rotavirus vaccine as part of routine childhood vaccination
153 [34–36]. Studies varied widely in their symptom definitions and diagnostic methodologies.

154

155 The size of studies included in this review varied widely. The number of symptomatic individuals assessed for
156 rotavirus in the included studies ranged from 101 to more than 280,000 (median: 371, IQR: 211 to 1,000).

157

158 ***Literature Synthesis***

159 Reported conditional rotavirus prevalence varied widely between the studies included in this review (Figure 2).
160 The reported percent of diarrhea cases due to rotavirus ranged from 0% to upwards of 30% within each age
161 strata. Similarly, the reported percent of diarrhea cases due to rotavirus varied widely by WHO region, with the
162 exception of Africa, which had the fewest data points. While larger studies tended to report lower prevalence
163 estimates, smaller studies reported conditional rotavirus prevalence that varied widely between 0 and 35%. The
164 biggest studies were conducted in Europe, South East Asia, and the Western Pacific regions.

165

166 ***Meta-Analysis***

167 The total pooled prevalence of diarrhea due to rotavirus among persons ≥ 5 years old in our analysis was 7.6%
168 (95% CI: 6.2–9.2%), an estimate that represents the average conditional prevalence of rotavirus in an average
169 study. The I^2 was 99.6%. The prediction interval, which reflects the heterogeneity of studies (i.e., settings), was 0
170 to 24%. This interval represents the range of probable values containing the true conditional prevalence of
171 rotavirus in older children and adults for future studies.

172

173 When examining diarrhea due to rotavirus by age strata, the pooled prevalence estimate was highest for older
174 children and adolescents and lowest for oldest adults, but heterogeneity remained high and prediction intervals
175 were broad for each age strata (Figure 3).

176

177 The calculated pooled prevalence of diarrhea due to rotavirus is presented by all secondary variables of interest
178 (WHO region, income region, study setting, study time period, diagnostic method, and symptom definitions) in
179 Table 3, with further disaggregation by age available in the Appendix 3. When examining diarrhea due to
180 rotavirus by geographic region, the pooled prevalence estimate was highest for the Americas, but the estimate
181 varied little between most regions, and as with age, each region had high heterogeneity and wide prediction
182 intervals. When examining diarrhea due to rotavirus by country's development status, pooled prevalence was
183 highest for the Upper-Middle Income region countries. This difference remained when excluding the 11 studies
184 from China (data not shown). Even so, heterogeneity remained high and prediction intervals remained broad for
185 each category.

186

187 Little variability in pooled prevalence, high heterogeneity, and broad prediction intervals were found when
188 examining diarrhea due to rotavirus by study setting, study time period, diagnostic method, and symptom
189 definitions (Table 3). Little variation existed when examining pooled prevalence for each of the secondary
190 variables of interest disaggregated by age strata (Table 3).

191

192 **Discussion**

193 In this systematic review and meta-analysis, we found the pooled prevalence of rotavirus among individuals with
194 diarrhea ≥ 5 years old was 7.6%, but prevalence varied widely between studies. When pooled by age and other
195 key variables of interest, we observed similar rotavirus prevalence across age groups, geographic regions,
196 country income levels, study types, diagnostic methods, symptom definitions, and time, ranging from
197 approximately 5–10%. Further examination of the pooled prevalence estimates by these variables revealed
198 broad ranges of reported conditional rotavirus prevalence across all observed categories. For example, the
199 ranges of reported conditional rotavirus prevalence were similar for each of the WHO regions and age strata.
200 Reported prediction intervals for pooled prevalence estimates were also broad, frequently ranging from 0–25%,
201 suggesting that the true prevalence of rotavirus among persons with diarrhea in unique future studies of the
202 specified groups could be anywhere from 0–25%. When examined by age group and another key variable
203 together (e.g., studies disaggregated by country income and age strata or diagnostic methods and age strata,
204 etc.), prevalence ranges narrowed for some groups, though most groups remained to have large prediction
205 intervals and/or the number of studies within a group were small and, therefore, it was difficult to draw
206 conclusions about a pooled prevalence estimate.

207

208 Large heterogeneity was expected given the large scope of this review. However, it was surprising that none of
209 the variables examined independently seemed to explain the heterogeneity. A few studies included in this
210 review found evidence of higher rotavirus prevalence among older children and/or older adults versus younger
211 adults [18,35,37–39]. However, not all studies demonstrated this phenomenon [24,32,40,41]. In reviews of
212 rotavirus prevalence in children under 5 years of age with diarrhea, certain regions have shown evidence of
213 higher prevalence [42,43]. However, in our review prevalence may be more country-dependent versus region-
214 dependent, highlighting the importance of context when examining rotavirus prevalence estimates. Even within

215 a single study, authors observed rotavirus prevalence change from 1% to 20% between two years [44].
216 Differences in study design, populations, and time could all contribute to different rotavirus prevalence. Further
217 disaggregation may be needed to identify stable conditional rotavirus prevalence estimates.
218 Our review highlighted a paucity of data on rotavirus in older children and adults from lower income settings,
219 particularly in Africa. This is particularly striking, as the burden of rotavirus in all populations is believed to be
220 the highest in Africa, and mortality from diarrhea in elderly populations has been found to be especially high in
221 select African countries [1]. Improved surveillance of diarrheal etiologies in populations greater than 5 years of
222 age—and publication of this surveillance, especially from African settings—would improve our understanding of
223 the burden of rotavirus and enable stronger inference to be made about rotavirus globally.

224

225 Almost all studies included in this meta-analysis were conducted prior to widescale implementation of the
226 rotavirus vaccine in the country of research, thus our data do not reflect the potential impact of rotavirus
227 vaccination rollout on older populations. However, some countries have examined how trends in rotavirus are
228 shifting in older children and adults after changes to national vaccination policy. For example, vaccine impact
229 studies in the United States and the United Kingdom showed lower rotavirus and gastroenteritis hospitalizations
230 in post-vaccine years, compared to pre-vaccine years [45,46]. These studies highlight the need to carefully
231 monitor the burden of rotavirus in older children and adults to strengthen evidence-based practices for rotavirus
232 control.

233

234 Tracking changes in conditional rotavirus prevalence over time is limited due to changes in diagnostic methods,
235 namely increased reliance on PCR testing in recent years. While this review required rotavirus to be laboratory
236 confirmed, the variation in diagnostic tests used in the included studies could mean differences in reported
237 conditional rotavirus prevalence are, at least in part, due to differences in sensitivity of the laboratory tests. For
238 example, studies relying on PCR tended to report higher levels of rotavirus than those relying on ELISA (see

239 Appendix 5F), which is not surprising, as PCR is the more sensitive test [47]. It is thus unsurprising that we
240 observed a higher conditional prevalence of rotavirus in older children and adults in more recent years (see
241 Appendix 5E), which is when PCR has also been more readily used. In other words, differences in diagnostics
242 could obscure true variations in rotavirus burden.

243

244 This study was subject to numerous other limitations. Firstly, the limits to the sensitivity of laboratory tests for
245 rotavirus mean that adults, which have been found to shed less virus than children when infected with rotavirus
246 [4], are at increased likelihood of having false negative results, which could under-estimate the prevalence of
247 rotavirus in this population. Secondly, the wide variations in age categories that studies used in reporting
248 rotavirus estimates created complexities in estimating rotavirus by age and limited our ability to make
249 inferences on specific age groups of interest (e.g., elderly populations). Similarly, the few studies available from
250 lower-income regions hindered us from making inference to the global distribution of rotavirus among older
251 children and adults experiencing diarrhea. We also experienced analytic challenges due to the wide range of
252 estimates found in this review; for example, it was common for extreme values to yield unstable estimates when
253 conducting sub-analyses with limited, often highly variable, data. Furthermore, we were unable to identify other
254 variables that may explain the heterogeneity of the prevalence estimates. Another limitation of our work is that
255 we did not formally assess risk of bias in individual studies, or risk of bias across studies. Finally, we examined
256 conditional prevalence of rotavirus, which although informative, does not enable us to make inference on the
257 overall burden of rotavirus experienced in any setting. To better inform rotavirus prevention programs and
258 policy, further research is necessary to identify and quantify the absolute number of older children and adults
259 experiencing rotavirus, including those who may have asymptomatic infections.

260

261 To the best of our knowledge, this is the first systematic review and meta-analysis in the published literature to
262 describe and quantify the prevalence of rotavirus occurring among older children and adults experiencing

263 diarrhea globally. Our review encompasses a large breadth of studies, including 66 papers conducted in more
264 than 30 countries, with research spanning the last three decades. While pooled estimates of rotavirus in older
265 children and adults are relatively low compared to estimates among children <5 years of age [48], some older
266 child and adult populations experienced rotavirus prevalence among diarrhea cases comparable to young
267 children. Furthermore, though outside the scope of this study, some etiology studies show rotavirus as one of
268 the most common pathogens in diarrhea patients within adult populations[14,49]. Understanding the burden of
269 rotavirus in these populations can be used to increase accuracy of global rotavirus estimates, improve our
270 understanding of where and between whom rotavirus is spreading, and highlight how this could differ with the
271 advent of widespread rotavirus vaccinations. Altogether, this understanding is critical to informing the funding,
272 research, and policy needed to improve rotavirus control globally in the post-vaccine era.

273

274 **Conclusions**

275 We conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis following PRISMA guidelines to assess the conditional
276 prevalence of rotavirus in older children and adults with diarrhea globally. Our study suggests the estimated
277 mean rotavirus prevalence in older children and adults with diarrhea is relatively low compared to the
278 prevalence among young children, but high heterogeneity suggests conditional rotavirus prevalence comparable
279 to young children in some settings. Minimal, if any, differences were observed for pooled conditional rotavirus
280 prevalence by age, geography, study design, or time, but a cautious interpretation is necessary due to the large
281 heterogeneity of data. These results can be used to support improved estimation of global rotavirus burden, but
282 there remains a need for improved surveillance systems or additional research on rotavirus in older children and
283 adults, especially in the African region, to strengthen our understanding of rotavirus infection in populations
284 over 5 years old.

285

286 **Acknowledgements:** We thank Dr. Laura Lamberti (Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, Enteric and Diarrheal
287 Diseases Team) for her subject matter expertise and review of this research and Ms. Jessie Seiler (University of
288 Washington, START Center) for her support in data collection.

289

290 **Conflict of Interest:** The authors report no conflicts of interest.

291

292

293 **Funding:** This work was completed by the Strategic, Analysis, Research, and Training Program (START) at the
294 University of Washington. START is a collaborative effort with, and is funded by, the Bill & Melinda Gates
295 Foundation. The funder commissioned the study but did not have exclusive control of the design, data collection
296 and analysis, decision to pursue publication, conclusions, or preparation of the manuscript.

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Table 1. Details for all studies included in meta-analysis (n=66 studies).

Author, year	Data Years	Country	WHO region	Income region	Study Setting	Vaccine in National Guidelines	Symptom Definition	Diagnostic	Ages (years) with reported data
Amarilla, 2007 [41]	2004-05	Paraguay	AMR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea, not defined	PAGE	18 to 27; 28 to 37; 38 to 57; 57+
Anderson, 2011 [51]	2005-06	United States	AMR	High	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea (Infectious Disease Society of America definition)	ELISA/EIA	24 to 89
Andersson, 2017 [52]	2010-14	Sweden	EUR	High	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined	PCR	6 to 10; 11 to 40; 41 to 70; 70+
Atchison, 2016 [53]	2013-14	United Kingdom	EUR	High	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	Not specified	5+
Bányai, 2003 [54]	1996-2000	Hungary	EUR	High	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	IC	5+
Barnes, 1997 [55]	1980-83	Australia	WPR	High	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea or vomiting for four days or fewer	Microscopy, ELISA/EIA, gel electrophoresis	5+
Bingnan, 1991 [56]	1987-89	Bangladesh	SEAR	Lower-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	ELISA/EIA	5 to 10; 10+
Bittencourt, 2000 [57]	1996-98	Brazil	AMR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	ELISA/EIA	5+
Breiman, 2014 [33]	2007- 10	Kenya	AFR	Lower-Middle	Community	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	ELISA/EIA	5 to 9; 10 to 17; 18 to 34; 35 to 49; 50+
Bresee, 2012 [50]	1999-01	United States	AMR	High	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	PCR	18 to 91
Carvalho-Costa, 2011 [38]	2005-09	Brazil	AMR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	ELISA/EIA, PAGE	5 to 12; 12 to 30; 30 to 60; 60+
Cheun, 2010 [39]	2004-06	Republic of Korea	WPR	High	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	ELISA/EIA	6 to 9; 10 to 49; 50+
Chowdhury, 2005 [58]	1996-01	Bangladesh	SEAR	Lower-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined	ELISA/EIA	5+

da Silva, 2017 [35]	2014	Brazil	AMR	Upper-Middle	Hospital and Community	Yes	Diarrhea not defined	ELISA/EIA, PAGE, PCR	5 to 10; 10+
Das, 2013 [59]	1993-2011	Bangladesh	SEAR	Lower-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Varied	ELISA/EIA	5 to 19; 19+
de Wit, 2001 [60]	1998-99	Netherlands	EUR	High	Community	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition) or diarrhea/ vomiting + symptoms	ELISA/EIA	5 to 11; 12+
de Wit, 2001 [61]	1996-99	Netherlands	EUR	High	Community	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition) or diarrhea/ vomiting + symptoms	ELISA/EIA	5 to 14; 15 to 29; 30 to 59; 60+
Degiuseppe, 2016 [62]	2012-14	Argentina	AMR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	ELISA/EIA, IC	5+
Elhag, 2013 [34]	2006-08	Sudan	AFR	Lower-Middle	Community	No	Diarrhea not defined	IC	5 to 14; 15+
Faruque, 2004 [42]	1996-01	Bangladesh	SEAR	Lower-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined	ELISA/EIA	5 to 14; 15 to 59; 60+
Fernández, 2010 [63]	2000-07	Spain	EUR	High	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined	ELISA/EIA	6 to 15; 16 to 64; 65 to 99
Fletcher, 2015 [36]	2007-10	Australia	WPR	High	Hospital, Unspecified	Yes	Liquid or watery stools taking the shape of the container	ELISA/EIA, IC	5 to 12; 13 to 24; 25 to 49; 50 to 74; 75+
Germani, 1994 [64]	1990-91	New Caledonia	WPR	High	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	IC	15+
Gong, 2018 [15]	2012-16	China	WPR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	PCR	18 to 29; 30 to 44; 44 to 59; 60+
Grassi, 2008 [65]	2004	Italy	EUR	High	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Two or more loose stools per day	ELISA/EIA, IC	5 to 16
Grytdal, 2016 [37]	2012-13	United States	AMR	High	Hospital, Outpatient	Yes	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	PCR	5 to 25; 26 to 45; 45 to 65; 65+
Hacimustafaoğlu, 2011 [66]	2007	Turkey	EUR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	ELISA/EIA	5 to 14
Hasing, 2009 [67]	2003-08	Ecuador	AMR	Upper-Middle	Community	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	IC	5 to 20; 20+

Hemming-Harlo, 2016 [68]	2009-13	Finland	EUR	High	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	PCR	5+
Hilmarsdóttir, 2011 [69]	2003-07	Iceland	EUR	High	Community	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	IC	5 to 29; 30 to 59
Huhulescu, 2008 [70]	2007	Austria	EUR	High	Community	No	Three or more loose stools within one 24-h period or diarrhea with two AGE symptoms	ELISA/EIA	5 to 19; 20 to 39; 40 to 59; 60+
Isabel, 2018 [71]	2009-15	Canada	AMR	High	Community	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	Microscopy, IC	5 to 19; 20+
Jain, 2016 [27]	2013-15	India	SEAR	Lower-Middle	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea, not defined	PCR	5+
Jain, 2016 [26]	2012-15	India	SEAR	Lower-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	ELISA/EIA, PCR	5+
Jansen, 2008 [72]	2005-07	Germany	EUR	High	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	PCR	18+
Jia, 2016 [16]	2012	China	WPR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Outpatient	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	ELISA/EIA	18 to 40; 41 to 60
Kittigul, 2014 [73]	2006-07	Thailand	SEAR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea, not defined (AGE specified)	PCR	18+
Konca, 2014 [74]	2012-13	Turkey	EUR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	ELISA/EIA	5 to 12 12+
Lahon, 2013 [28]	1994-95; 2004-10	India	SEAR	Lower-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	ELISA/EIA, PCR	11+
Luchs, 2014 [45]	2004-11	Brazil	AMR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	ELISA/EIA, PAGE, PCR	18+
Mladenova, 2010 [75]	2005-08	Bulgaria	EUR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	ELISA/EIA	5+
Nair, 2010 [29]	2007-09	India	SEAR	Lower-Middle	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea not defined	PAGE	5+
Nakajima, 2001 [76]	1996-99	Japan	WPR	High	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined	ELISA/EIA	18+
Nakamura, 2016 [77]	2008-14	Japan	WPR	High	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	PCR	6+
Nayak, 2018 [30]	2012-13	India	SEAR	Lower-Middle	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea not defined	ELISA/EIA	5+
Nilsson, 2000 [78]	1996-97	Sweden	EUR	High	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea not defined	Microscopy	15+
Podkolzin, 2009 [40]	2005-07	Russian Federation	EUR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	PCR	5 to 14; 18+

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Sethi, 2001 [79]	1993-96	United Kingdom	EUR	High	Community	No	Loose stool or vomiting lasting less than two weeks	ELISA/EIA	5 to 15	
Shen, 2013 [18]	2010-11	China	WPR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	ELISA/EIA	15+	
Steenland, 2013 [80]	2012-13	Haiti	AMR	Low	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	ELISA/EIA	5 to 17; 18 to 65	
Stroni, 2014 [81]	2010-12	Albania	EUR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	PCR	15+	
Szücs, 1999 [82]	1993-96	Hungary	EUR	High	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea not defined	ELISA/EIA, IC	5 to 14	
Tatte, 2014 [31]	2008-12	India	SEAR	Lower-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	ELISA/EIA	10+	
Tatte, 2010 [83]	1993-96; 2004-07	India	SEAR	Lower-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	ELISA/EIA	10 to 18; 18+	
Thongprachum, 2015 [84]	2009-13	Japan	WPR	High	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	PCR	5+	
Uchida, 2006 [85]	2003-04	Nepal	SEAR	Low	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined	ELISA/EIA	5 to 14; 15+	
Unal, 2016 [86]	2009-13	Turkey	EUR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Inpatient	No	Diarrhea not defined (AGE specified)	IC	7 to 10; 11 to 20; 21+	
Wang, 2017 [19]	2014-15	China	WPR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Outpatient	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	IC	15+	
Wang, 2007 [20]	2000-03; 2003-06	China	WPR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined	PAGE	6 to 14; 15 to 19; 20 to 29; 30 to 39; 40 to 49; 50 to 59; 60 to 69; 70+	
Wang, 2009 [21]	2006-08	China	WPR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	PAGE	15+	
Wang, 2011 [22]	2008-11	China	WPR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	PAGE	15 to 90	
Zhang, 2017 [23]	2014-15	China	WPR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	PCR	5 to 65	
Zhang, 2016 [24]	2014-15	China	WPR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Outpatient	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	PCR	5 to 15; 15 to 50; 50+	
Zhang, 2017 [25]	2009-14	China	WPR	Upper-Middle	Hospital, Outpatient	No	Diarrhea (WHO definition)	ELISA/EIA	65+	

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Zhirakovskaia, 2016 [87]	2006-11	Russian Federation	EUR	Upper- Middle	Hospital, Unspecified	No	Diarrhea not defined	PCR	16 +
Zhu, 2013 [17]	2007	China	WPR	Upper- Middle	Hospital, Outpatient	No	WHO definition	PCR	20 to 49; 50+

WHO = World Health Organization; AFR = African Region; AMR = Region of the Americas; EUR = European Region; SEAR = South-East Asia Region; WPR = Western Pacific Region; AGE = acute gastroenteritis; IC = immunochromatography; ELISA = enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; EIA = enzyme immunoassay; PAGE = polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis; PCR = polymerase chain reaction

Table 2. Summary of studies included in systematic review and meta-analysis (n=66)

Category	Studies n (%)
Study location by WHO region	
Africa	2 (3%)
Americas	12 (18%)
South-East Asia	13 (20%)
Europe	21 (32%)
Eastern Mediterranean	0 (0%)
Western Pacific	18 (27%)
Study type	
Hospital surveillance	56 (85%)
Community surveillance	9 (14%)
Hospital and community surveillance	1 (2%)
Income region	
Low	2 (3%)
Lower-Middle	13 (20%)
Upper-Middle	26 (39%)
High	25 (38%)
Setting	
Hospital: inpatient	20 (30%)
Hospital: outpatient	6 (9%)
Hospital: unspecified	31 (47%)
Community	9 (14%)
Study period	
Before 2000	4 (6%)
2000 to 2009	18 (27%)
2010 to present	44 (66%)
Study scope	
Rotavirus only	33 (50%)
Symptom definition	
WHO definition	24 (36%)
Diagnostic method*	
ELISA/EIA	25 (38%)
PCR	16 (24%)
PAGE	5 (8%)
Microscopy	1 (2%)
Multiple	11 (17%)
Rotavirus vaccine in national policy	3 (4.5%)

ELISA = enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; EIA = enzyme immunoassay; PCR = polymerase chain reaction; PAGE = polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis

*One study did not specify a diagnostic method.

Table 3. Pooled conditional rotavirus prevalence and corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CI), heterogeneity (I^2), and 95% prediction intervals (PI).

Secondary Variables of Interest	Pooled Prevalence (95% CI)	I^2	95% PI
Total Prevalence	7.6 (6.2–9.2)	100	0–24
WHO Region			
AFR	7.6 (6.4–9.0)	--	--
AMR	10.3 (5.2–16.9)	98	0–39
EMR	-- --	--	--
EUR	6.8 (4.3–9.8)	99	0–24
SEAR	7.3 (4.6–10.5)	97	0–22
WPR	7.2 (4.7–10.2)	98	0–23
Income			
High	6.1 (3.7–9.0)	100	0–25
Upper-Middle	10.2 (7.8–12.8)	95	1–26
Lower-Middle and Low	6.2 (4.2–8.5)	97	1–17
Study Setting			
Community	7.1 (3.7–11.4)	92	0–24
Hospital, Inpatient	8.6 (5.3–12.6)	100	0–31
Hospital, Outpatient	5.4 (1.9–10.7)	94	0–24
Hospital, Unspecified	7.1 (5.4–9.0)	98	1–20
Hospital and Community	34.8 (28.5–41.3)	--	--
Study Period			
<2000	5.5 (3.0–8.6)	98	0–22
2000-2009	8.1 (6.0–10.5)	98	1–23
>2009	8.4 (5.6–11.7)	100	0–28
Symptom Definition			
WHO Diarrhea Definition	7.3 (5.1–10.0)	98	0–23
Non-WHO Definition	7.8 (5.9–9.9)	100	0–25
Diagnostic Methods			
ELISA/EIA	5.8 (4.4–7.5)	96	1–16
PCR	9.0 (5.5–13.2)	98	0–30
Other/Mixed	8.7 (5.9–12.0)	100	0–30

WHO = World Health Organization; AFR = African Region; AMR = Region of the Americas; EUR = European Region; SEAR = South-East Asia Region; WPR = Western Pacific Region; ELISA = enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; EIA = enzyme immunoassay; PCR = polymerase chain reaction

Figure 1. Flow diagram following for article selection, following PRISMA guidelines

Figure 2. Percent of diarrhea cases due to rotavirus by age strata (2A) and WHO region (2B). Each circle represents a “data point” within a study. A data point is defined as number of rotavirus cases (numerator) among number of diarrhea cases (denominator) for a specific age group. Studies may have more than one data point/circle if data were disaggregated by age. Circle size corresponds to sample size (range: 100-200,000+ people). (2A) Data points were organized into the first three age strata: “Older Children” including ages 5–20 years, “Adults: Younger” including ages 15–50 years, “Adults: Older” including ages 50 years and older. Data points that could not fit into one of the first three age strata were categorized into “Adults of Any Age” and/or “Broad Ages.” A study is represented once within an age stratum, but may contribute to more than one age strata (i.e., have more than one circle across age strata). (2B) The same age-disaggregated data described above were organized by WHO Region. Multiple circles from the same study can be represented within the same WHO region, but correspond to unique data within the study. No studies are in multiple categories.

2A: Rotavirus by Age Strata

2B: Rotavirus by WHO Region

Figure 3. Forest plots of conditional rotavirus prevalence by age strata and all studies. Forest plots of rotavirus prevalence among persons with diarrhea were organized into three age strata: (3A) Older children and adolescents include ages 5 to 20 years, (3B) Younger adults include ages 15 to 50 years, and (3C) Older adults include ages 50 years and older. Study data spanning multiple age strata were not included in these three plots. For forest plots of study data spanning broad age ranges (i.e., multiple age strata), refer to Appendix 4. Figure (3D) includes all 66 studies in the meta-analysis.

3A: Older children and adolescents (n=25 studies)

3B: Younger adults (n=8 studies)

3C: Older adults (n=14 studies)

3D: All studies (n=66 studies)

Study (Age Range)	Cases	Denominator	Rotavirus Prevalence	Point Prev	95% CI	Weight
Germani 1994 (15-100)	0	420		0.00	[0.00; 0.01]	1.5%
Atchison 2016 (5-100)	343	287724	■	0.00	[0.00; 0.00]	1.6%
Bingnan 1991 (5-100)	23	2370	■	0.01	[0.01; 0.01]	1.6%
Steenland 2013 (5-65)	17	1188	■	0.01	[0.01; 0.02]	1.6%
Zhu 2013 (20-100)	9	513	■	0.02	[0.01; 0.03]	1.5%
Fletcher 2015 (5-100)	19	1080	■	0.02	[0.01; 0.03]	1.6%
Grytdal 2016 (5-100)	20	1031	■	0.02	[0.01; 0.03]	1.6%
de Wit 2001 (5-100)	17	681	■	0.02	[0.02; 0.04]	1.5%
Zhirakovskaia 2016 (16-100)	3	107	■	0.03	[0.01; 0.09]	1.3%
Andersson 2017 (6-100)	451	15951	■	0.03	[0.03; 0.03]	1.6%
Anderson 2011 (24-89)	18	620	■	0.03	[0.02; 0.05]	1.5%
de Wit 2001 (5-100)	7	235	■	0.03	[0.01; 0.06]	1.5%
Nilsson 2000 (15-100)	23	750	■	0.03	[0.02; 0.05]	1.5%
Cheun 2010 (6-100)	949	30589	■	0.03	[0.03; 0.03]	1.6%
Das 2013 (5-100)	816	22909	■	0.04	[0.03; 0.04]	1.6%
Zhang 2017 (65-100)	149	3857	■	0.04	[0.03; 0.05]	1.6%
Fernández 2010 (6-99)	82	1998	■	0.04	[0.03; 0.05]	1.6%
Huhulescu 2008 (5-89)	12	286	■	0.04	[0.02; 0.07]	1.5%
Faruque 2004 (5-100)	267	5723	■	0.05	[0.04; 0.05]	1.6%
Chowdury 2005 (5-100)	283	5653	■	0.05	[0.04; 0.06]	1.6%
Bányai 2003 (5-14)	16	304	■	0.05	[0.03; 0.09]	1.5%
Grassi 2008 (5-16)	16	284	■	0.06	[0.03; 0.09]	1.5%
Uchida 2006 (5-100)	37	645	■	0.06	[0.04; 0.08]	1.5%
Lahon 2013 (11-100)	56	951	■	0.06	[0.05; 0.08]	1.6%
Sethi 2001 (5-15)	19	319	■	0.06	[0.04; 0.09]	1.5%
Nayak 2018 (5-100)	44	728	■	0.06	[0.04; 0.08]	1.5%
Stroni 2014 (15-100)	64	1000	■	0.06	[0.05; 0.08]	1.6%
Tatte 2010 (10-100)	112	1554	■	0.07	[0.06; 0.09]	1.6%
Bittencourt 2000 (5-100)	8	109	■	0.07	[0.03; 0.14]	1.3%
Zhang 2016 (5-100)	20	271	■	0.07	[0.05; 0.11]	1.5%
Unal 2016 (7-100)	48	650	■	0.07	[0.06; 0.10]	1.5%
Zhang 2017 (5-65)	17	224	■	0.08	[0.05; 0.12]	1.5%
Breiman 2014 (5-100)	162	2132	■	0.08	[0.07; 0.09]	1.6%
Wang 2009 (15-100)	83	1088	■	0.08	[0.06; 0.09]	1.6%
Hilmarsdóttir 2011 (5-83)	28	361	■	0.08	[0.05; 0.11]	1.5%
Elhag 2013 (5-100)	30	380	■	0.08	[0.05; 0.11]	1.5%
Degliuseppe 2016 (5-100)	275	3459	■	0.08	[0.07; 0.09]	1.6%
Gong 2018 (18-100)	714	8783	■	0.08	[0.08; 0.09]	1.6%
Thongprachum 2015 (5-100)	13	156	■	0.08	[0.05; 0.14]	1.4%
Konca 2014 (5-100)	52	583	■	0.09	[0.07; 0.12]	1.5%
Isabel 2018 (5-100)	36	391	■	0.09	[0.07; 0.13]	1.5%
Carvalho-Costa 2011 (5-100)	160	1728	■	0.09	[0.08; 0.11]	1.6%
Shen 2013 (15-100)	138	1479	■	0.09	[0.08; 0.11]	1.6%
Luchs 2014 (18-100)	197	2102	■	0.09	[0.08; 0.11]	1.6%
Tatte 2014 (10-100)	35	371	■	0.09	[0.07; 0.13]	1.5%
Nair 2010 (5-100)	181	1871	■	0.10	[0.08; 0.11]	1.6%
Podkolzin 2009 (5-100)	184	1714	■	0.11	[0.09; 0.12]	1.6%
Wang 2017 (15-100)	48	441	■	0.11	[0.08; 0.14]	1.5%
Wang 2007 (6-100)	275	2477	■	0.11	[0.10; 0.12]	1.6%
Jia 2016 (18-60)	35	312	■	0.11	[0.08; 0.15]	1.5%
Nakamura 2016 (6-100)	35	309	■	0.11	[0.08; 0.16]	1.5%
Jansen 2008 (18-100)	12	104	■	0.12	[0.06; 0.20]	1.3%
Wang 2011 (15-90)	96	795	■	0.12	[0.10; 0.15]	1.5%
Hacimustafaoglu 2011 (5-14)	46	368	■	0.12	[0.09; 0.16]	1.5%
Jain 2016 (5-100)	24	176	■	0.14	[0.09; 0.20]	1.4%
Jain 2016 (5-100)	51	360	■	0.14	[0.11; 0.18]	1.5%
Szűcs 1999 (5-14)	188	1235	■	0.15	[0.13; 0.17]	1.6%
Mladenova 2010 (5-100)	45	293	■	0.15	[0.12; 0.20]	1.5%
Nakajima 2001 (18-100)	108	683	■	0.16	[0.13; 0.19]	1.5%
Barnes 1997 (5-100)	45	282	■	0.16	[0.12; 0.21]	1.5%
Bresee 2012 (18-91)	19	106	■	0.18	[0.11; 0.27]	1.3%
Amarilla 2007 (18-100)	155	801	■	0.19	[0.17; 0.22]	1.5%
Kittigui 2014 (18-100)	27	131	■	0.21	[0.14; 0.29]	1.4%
Hasing 2009 (5-100)	56	249	■	0.22	[0.18; 0.28]	1.5%
Hemming-Harfo 2016 (5-15)	49	150	■	0.33	[0.25; 0.41]	1.4%
da Silva 2017 (5-100)	73	210	■	0.35	[0.28; 0.42]	1.4%

Overall Effect
Prediction Interval
 Heterogeneity: $I^2 = 100\%$, $\tau^2 = 0.0128$, $\rho = 0$

Appendix 1. Search strings used to identify articles for systematic review

PubMed

('rotavirus'/exp OR 'rotavirus' OR 'human rotavirus'/exp OR 'human rotavirus' OR 'rotavirus infection'/exp OR 'rotavirus infection' OR rotavirus:ti,ab OR rotaviruses:ti,ab) AND ('prevalence'/exp OR 'mortality'/exp OR burden:ti OR etiology:ti OR aetiology:ti OR mortality:ti OR death:ti OR deaths:ti OR fatal:ti OR fatality:ti OR epidemiology:ti) AND [1990-3000]/py AND [humans]/lim NOT ('colitis':ti,ab OR enterocolitis:ti,ab OR 'inflammatory bowel':ti,ab OR irritable:ti,ab OR crohn*:ti,ab OR hiv:ti OR treatment:ti OR appendicitis:ti,ab OR esophag*:ti,ab OR surger*:ti,ab OR gastritis:ti,ab OR liver:ti,ab OR 'case report':ti OR 'case-report':ti OR outbreak*:ti OR travel*:ti OR therapy:ti OR 'conference abstract'/it)

Embase

('rotavirus'/exp OR 'rotavirus' OR 'human rotavirus'/exp OR 'human rotavirus' OR 'rotavirus infection'/exp OR 'rotavirus infection' OR rotavirus:ti,ab OR rotaviruses:ti,ab) AND ('prevalence'/exp OR 'mortality'/exp OR burden:ti OR etiology:ti OR aetiology:ti OR mortality:ti OR death:ti OR deaths:ti OR fatal:ti OR fatality:ti OR epidemiology:ti) AND [1990-3000]/py AND [humans]/lim NOT ('colitis':ti,ab OR enterocolitis:ti,ab OR 'inflammatory bowel':ti,ab OR irritable:ti,ab OR crohn*:ti,ab OR hiv:ti OR treatment:ti OR appendicitis:ti,ab OR esophag*:ti,ab OR surger*:ti,ab OR gastritis:ti,ab OR liver:ti,ab OR 'case report':ti OR 'case-report':ti OR outbreak*:ti OR travel*:ti OR therapy:ti OR 'conference abstract'/it)

Appendix 2. Distribution of countries where studies included in this systematic review and meta-analysis were conducted. Studies included were conducted in China and India (>4 studies each); Bangladesh, Brazil, Japan, Turkey, and the United States (3-4 studies each); Australia, Hungary, Netherlands, Russia, Spain, Sweden, and the United Kingdom (2 studies each), and Bulgaria, Austria, Albania, Argentina, Cameroon, Canada, Ecuador, Finland, Germany, Haiti, Iceland, Italy, Kenya, Nepal, South Korea, Sudan, Thailand, and Paraguay (1 study each).

Appendix 3: Pooled conditional rotavirus prevalence and corresponding 95% Confidence Intervals (CI), heterogeneity (I²), and 95% Prediction Intervals (PI) by secondary variables and age group

Variable	Older Children and Adolescents			Younger Adults			Older Adults			Broad Adult Ages			All Ages			Total		
	CP (CI)	I ²	PI	CP (CI)	I ²	PI	CP (CI)	I ²	PI	CP (CI)	I ²	PI	CP (CI)	I ²	PI	CP (CI)	I ²	PI
Prevalence	8.7 (6.2–11.7)	96	0–27	5.4 (1.4–11.8)	96	0–31	4.7 (2.8–7.0)	96	0–16	6.9 (4.9–9.2)	97	0–24	6.8 (4.7–9.2)	99	0–23	7.6 (6.2–9.2)	100	0–24
WHO Region																		
AFR	6.6 (6.4–6.8)	0	--	8.4 (6.9–10.0)	--	--	5.8 (3.0–9.4)	--	--	9.1 (5.5–13.5)	--	--	--	--	--	7.6 (6.4–9.0)	--	--
AMR	12.2 (2.6–27.3)	91	0–64	7.8 (0.0–100.0)	98	--	8.2 (0.0–30.3)	91	0–100	7.8 (2.3–16.1)	97	0–41	9.4 (0.5–27.3)	97	0–68	10.3 (5.2–16.9)	98	0–39
EMR	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
EUR	9.6 (5.0–15.6)	95	0–35	--	--	--	3.0 (2.4–3.6)	0	2–5	4.6 (2.8–6.9)	93	0–13	5.0 (2.1–9.0)	99	0–21	6.8 (4.3–9.8)	99	0–24
SEAR	4.3 (1.0–9.9)	93	0–24	--	--	--	4.2 (2.6–6.2)	--	--	7.0 (1.7–15.5)	94	0–36	7.3 (3.8–11.8)	97	0–24	7.3 (4.6–10.5)	97	0–22
WPR	11.6 (1.3–30.3)	96	0–100	4.1 (0.1–13.2)	96	0–38	4.1 (1.0–9.2)	98	0–23	8.6 (3.6–15.4)	97	0–34	6.8 (2.6–12.8)	95	0–28	7.2 (4.7–10.2)	98	0–23
Income																		
High	8.5 (4.4–13.7)	94	0–30	0.4 (0.0–58.3)	88	--	2.4 (1.4–3.8)	76	0–6	4.3 (1.7–7.8)	96	0–22	4.2 (1.9–7.5)	99	0–19	6.1 (3.7–9.0)	100	0–25
Upper-Middle	16.1 (11.3–21.5)	80	5–31	8.2 (2.3–17.2)	95	0–38	7.6 (3.2–13.7)	96	0–28	11.0 (7.9–14.7)	88	2–27	10.3 (5.3–16.6)	93	0–34	10.2 (7.8–12.8)	95	1–26
Lower-Middle and Low	4.7 (2.5–7.6)	90	0–15	8.4 (6.9–10.0)	--	--	4.7 (0.0–17.3)	0	--	4.5 (1.9–8.1)	94	0–17	7.3 (3.8–11.8)	97	0–24	6.2 (4.2–8.5)	97	1–17
Study Setting																		
Community	8.2 (2.6–16.7)	89	0–36	8.4 (6.9–10.0)	--	--	4.6 (0.0–36.9)	27	--	6.0 (1.0–15.0)	91	0–38	4.6 (2.1–7.9)	19	1–11	7.1 (3.7–11.4)	92	0–24

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Hospital, Inpatient	12.4 (6.1–20.5)	95	0–41	-- -- --	2.4 (2.2–2.7)	-- --	6.3 (1.9–13.0)	96	0–31	7.2 (2.6–13.8)	100	0–32	8.6 (5.3–12.6)	100	0–31			
Hospital, Outpatient	-- -- --	--	--	3.7 (0.8–21.3)	92	0–100	3.3 (1.3–6.2)	37	0–22	7.5 (0.1–30.5)	94	0–100	3.7 (0.0–90.1)	91	--	5.4 (1.9–10.7)	94	0–24
Hospital, Unspecified	6.7 (3.7–10.5)	96	0–22	6.1 (0.2–26.2)	98	0–81	6.0 (2.6–10.8)	97	0–24	7.3 (4.4–10.9)	98	0–26	6.3 (4.1–8.9)	96	0–18	7.1 (5.4–9.0)	98	1–20
Hospital and Community	-- -- --	--	--	-- -- --	--	--	-- -- --	--	--	-- -- --	--	--	34.8 (28.5–41.3)	--	--	34.8 (28.5–41.3)	--	--
Study Period																		
<2000	5.3 (1.7–10.7)	96	0–25	-- -- --	--	--	4.0 (0.1–13.1)	0	--	4.0 (0.3–11.4)	98	0–32	5.4 (2.1–10.1)	96	0–22	5.5 (3.0–8.6)	98	0–22
2000–2009	9.7 (6.1–13.9)	97	1–27	5.3 (0.1–18.2)	98	0–53	5.2 (1.9–10.0)	96	0–23	9.0 (6.1–12.4)	96	1–26	6.0 (2.3–11.3)	97	0–25	8.1 (6.0–10.5)	98	1–23
>2009	11.4 (2.1–26.7)	95	0–61	5.6 (0.0–22.1)	91	0–100	4.4 (1.2–9.4)	98	1–24	5.2 (2.1–9.5)	98	0–23	7.9 (4.4–12.3)	99	0–30	8.4 (5.6–11.7)	100	0–28
Symptom Definition																		
WHO Diarrhea Definition	9.0 (2.7–18.4)	96	0–43	6.3 (1.4–14.3)	91	0–36	4.3 (1.6–8.3)	98	0–18	8.5 (4.6–13.3)	97	0–30	6.1 (2.6–10.8)	97	0–23	7.3 (5.1–10.0)	98	0–23
Non-WHO Definition	8.6 (5.8–12.0)	96	0–26	4.6 (0.0–24.7)	98	0–82	5.0 (2.2–8.8)	94	0–20	5.9 (3.7–8.7)	96	0–22	7.0 (4.4–10.1)	99	0–25	7.8 (5.9–9.9)	100	0–25
Diagnostic Methods																		
ELISA/EIA	5.2 (3.3–7.6)	94	0–15	8.7 (2.1–19.2)	0	--	3.5 (2.5–4.6)	84	2–6	5.2 (2.9–8.0)	96	0–18	5.6 (3.4–8.5)	96	0–17	5.8 (4.4–7.5)	96	1–16
PCR	17.7 (0.1–62.0)	98	53–0	3.1 (0.0–13.0)	94	63–91	3.9 (0.6–9.7)	98	2–27	7.8 (3.6–13.4)	97	0–29	6.8 (3.1–11.7)	92	0–23	9.0 (5.5–13.2)	98	0–30
Other/Mixed	11.5 (7.7–15.8)	89	2–27	5.9 (0.0–51.2)	99	2–12	7.6 (0.3–23.3)	97	14–65	8.1 (3.7–13.8)	96	0–34	8.0 (3.2–14.7)	100	1–37	8.7 (5.9–12.0)	100	0–30

WHO = World Health Organization; AFR = African Region; AMR = Region of the Americas; EUR = European Region; SEAR = South-East Asia Region; WPR = Western Pacific Region; ELISA = enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; EIA = enzyme immunoassay; PCR = polymerase chain reaction

Appendix 4: Forest plots of conditional rotavirus prevalence by broad age strata. Study data spanning large age ranges (i.e., could not be disaggregated into smaller age ranges) were organized into (4A) Broad adult ages or (4B) Broad all ages forest plots. (4A) Forest plot of broad adult ages includes study data of persons 15+ years. (4B) Forest plot of broad all ages includes study data of persons 5+ years. Additional forest plots by age strata, including for all 66 studies, can be found in Figure 3.

Appendix 4A: Broad adult age groups (n=33 studies)

Appendix 4B: Broad all age groups (n=29 studies)

Appendix 5: Estimated pooled conditional rotavirus prevalence for age strata, WHO region, income region, study setting, study time period, diagnostic method, and symptom definition.

Appendix 5A: Conditional prevalence by age strata

Appendix 5B: Conditional prevalence by WHO region

Appendix 5C: Conditional prevalence by income region

Appendix 5D: Conditional prevalence by study setting

Appendix 5E: Conditional prevalence by study period

Appendix 5F: Conditional prevalence by diagnostic method

